

Article title

Author 1,

Affiliation of Author 1
Affiliation of Author 2
Affiliation of Author 3

Journal title, Vol. 18 No. 3 (2024), 8519, <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>

Abstract

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi condimentum viverra nulla. Maecenas ligula odio, rutrum quis justo nec, ornare finibus felis. Proin rhoncus, libero quis porttitor sollicitudin, leo mi laoreet turpis, quis bibendum dui tellus quis diam. Cras volutpat id urna ut ullamcorper. Morbi euismod tristique lacus ut lobortis. Morbi sagittis interdum urna, eget rhoncus dolor tincidunt ut. Vestibulum orci magna, pellentesque sit amet ex in, finibus sodales augue.

Keywords

keyword 1, keyword 2, keyword 3, keyword 4, keyword 5

Supporting information

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567>

Author contributions

Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing; Author 2: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization, Investigation. Author 3: Supervision, Software, Validation

Funding information

This research is supported by the Research Funder X Grant No.1234-5678.

References

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

XYZ is an international, open-access, peer-reviewed academic journal published by the University ABC.
eISSN XXXX-XXXX ISSN XXXX-XXXX

Download full text

Submitted 5 January 2024
Reviewed 10 March 2024
Accepted 30 April 2024
Published 3 May 2024

How to Cite

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3. (2024).
Article title. Journal title, 18(3), 8516.
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>.

Style

Copyright (c) 2024 Authors

This work is licensed under a
[Creative Commons Attribution
4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Article Information

- Article Title:** The title of the research article.
- Journal title, volume, issue, publication year, and article number (or pagination)**
- Abstract:** A concise summary that highlights the study's objectives, methods, key findings, and conclusions.
- Keywords:** Specific terms or phrases that capture the main topics of the study. It is a good idea to enrich author-provided keywords with terms from relevant controlled vocabularies.
- Persistent Identifier (DOI, ARK, Handle, URN):** DOI should always be displayed as a full URL link in the form <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/xxxxx>. Learn more: <https://www.crossref.org/display-guidelines/>
- Publication timeline :** Dates of article submission, review, acceptance and publication.
- Funding information:** A statement disclosing financial support received for the research or project. This section typically includes details about grants, sponsorships, institutional support, or other financial resources that contributed to the study. It often specifies the funding organisations or agencies (using funders' persistent identifiers, e.g. RORs, is recommended), grant numbers, and any relevant funding acknowledgements.

Article title

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3

Affiliation of Author 1
Affiliation of Author 2
Affiliation of Author 3

Journal title, Vol. 18 No. 3 (2024), 8519,
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>

Abstract
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi condimentum viverra nulla. Maecenas ligula odio, rutrum quis justo nec, ornare finibus felis. Proin rhoncus, libero quis porttitor sollicitudin, leo mi laoreet turpis, quis bibendum dui tellus quis diam. Cras volutpat id urna ut ullamcorper. Morbi euismod tristique lacus ut lobortis. Morbi sagittis interdum urna, eget rhoncus dolor tincidunt ut. Vestibulum orci magna, pellentesque sit amet ex in, finibus sodales augue.

Keywords
keyword 1, keyword 2, keyword 3, keyword 4, keyword 5

Supporting information
Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567>

Author contributions
Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing; Author 2: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization, Investigation. Author 3: Supervision, Software, Validation

Funding information
This research is supported by the Research Funder X Grant No.1234-5678.

References
Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Download full text

Submitted 5 January 2024
Reviewed 10 March 2024
Accepted 30 April 2024
Published 3 May 2024

How to Cite
Author 1, Author 2, Author 3. (2024).
Article title. Journal title, 18(3), 8516.
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>.

Style

Copyright (c) 2024 Authors

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Author information

- 1. Full names of authors:** See Author contributions for more details
- 2. ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID):** Unique identifiers for each author.
- 3. Institutional affiliations:** Authors' institutions, including full names and addresses, e.g. University, Faculty/Institute, City, Country
- 4. ROR (Research Organization Registry ID):** Institutional persistent identifier
- 5. Author Contributions:** Contributions for deserving authorship include not only writing but also the activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of the research data/materials, analysis and interpretation. Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) to describe the key types of contributions made to the article. See Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) below for more information.

Article title

Author 1,

Affiliation of Author 1
Affiliation of Author 2
Affiliation of Author 3

Journal title, Vol. 18 No. 3 (2024), 8519,
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>

Abstract

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi condimentum viverra nulla. Maecenas ligula odio, rutrum quis justo nec, ornare finibus felis. Proin rhoncus, libero quis porttitor sollicitudin, leo mi laoreet turpis, quis bibendum dui tellus quis diam. Cras volutpat id urna ut ullamcorper. Morbi euismod tristique lacus ut lobortis. Morbi sagittis interdum urna, eget rhoncus dolor tincidunt ut. Vestibulum orci magna, pellentesque sit amet ex in, finibus sodales augue.

Keywords

keyword 1, keyword 2, keyword 3, keyword 4, keyword 5

Supporting information

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567>

Author contributions

Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing; Author 2: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization, Investigation. Author 3: Supervision, Software, Validation

Funding information

This research is supported by the Research Funder X Grant No.1234-5678.

References

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Download full text

Submitted 5 January 2024
Reviewed 10 March 2024
Accepted 30 April 2024
Published 3 May 2024

How to Cite

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3. (2024).
Article title. Journal title, 18(3), 8516.
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>.

Style

Copyright (c) 2024 Authors

This work is licensed under a
[Creative Commons Attribution
4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Journal and publisher information

- Journal title** : it should be the same as registered in the ISSN International Registry. Don't use any unofficial translated or abbreviated forms.
- Publisher's name**. Display the publisher's name prominently on the journal website. Use the official name, as registered in the ISSN International Registry.
- ISSN and eISSN**. ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) and eISSN (electronic ISSN) are unique identifiers assigned to print and electronic versions of a serial publication, respectively. Display these numbers prominently on a journal website to make it easy for users to locate and verify this information.

Article title

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3

Affiliation of Author 1
Affiliation of Author 2
Affiliation of Author 3

Journal title, Vol. 18 No. 3 (2024), 8519,
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>

Abstract

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi condimentum viverra nulla. Maecenas ligula odio, rutrum quis justo nec, ornare finibus felis. Proin rhoncus, libero quis porttitor sollicitudin, leo mi laoreet turpis, quis bibendum dui tellus quis diam. Cras volutpat id urna ut ullamcorper. Morbi euismod tristique lacus ut lobortis. Morbi sagittis interdum urna, eget rhoncus dolor tincidunt ut. Vestibulum orci magna, pellentesque sit amet ex in, finibus sodales augue.

Keywords

keyword 1, keyword 2, keyword 3, keyword 4, keyword 5

Supporting information

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567>

Author contributions

Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing; Author 2: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization, Investigation. Author 3: Supervision, Software, Validation

Funding information

This research is supported by the Research Funder X Grant No.1234-5678.

References

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

XYZ is an international, open-access, peer-reviewed academic journal published by the University ABC.

eISSN XXXX-XXXX ISSN XXXX-XXXX

Submitted 5 January 2024
Reviewed 10 March 2024
Accepted 30 April 2024
Published 3 May 2024

How to Cite

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3. (2024).
Article title. Journal title, 18(3), 8516.
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>.

Style

Copyright (c) 2024 Authors

This work is licensed under a
[Creative Commons Attribution
4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Rights and access Information

- Open access icon** : indicates the open access status of the article.
- Copyright information** : Specifies who has the legal rights to the article.
Diamond OA journals should allow authors to retain copyright.
- Licence information** : Outlines the terms under which the article can be used, shared, and adapted by others. The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence is recommended, as it allows unrestricted distribution and adaptation of the work, provided the original authors are credited. Use the latest version of the CC licence: 4.0 version, which is more user-friendly and more internationally robust. Always provide a link to the licence deed. Learn more: <https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/policies/displaying-licensing-information>

Article title

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3

Affiliation of Author 1
Affiliation of Author 2
Affiliation of Author 3

Journal title, Vol. 18 No. 3 (2024), 8519,
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>

Abstract

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi condimentum viverra nulla. Maecenas ligula odio, rutrum quis justo nec, ornare finibus felis. Proin rhoncus, libero quis porttitor sollicitudin, leo mi laoreet turpis, quis bibendum dui tellus quis diam. Cras volutpat id urna ut ullamcorper. Morbi euismod tristique lacus ut lobortis. Morbi sagittis interdum urna, eget rhoncus dolor tincidunt ut. Vestibulum orci magna, pellentesque sit amet ex in, finibus sodales augue.

Keywords

keyword 1, keyword 2, keyword 3, keyword 4, keyword 5

Supporting information

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567>

Author contributions

Author 1: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing; Author 2: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Visualization, Investigation. Author 3: Supervision, Software, Validation

Funding information

This research is supported by the Research Funder X Grant No.1234-5678.

References

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Author, A. A., & Author, B. B. (Date of publication). Title of article. Title of journal, volume number(issue number), page range. doi: 0000000/000000000000

Download full text

Submitted 5 January 2024
Reviewed 10 March 2024
Accepted 30 April 2024
Published 3 May 2024

How to Cite

Author 1, Author 2, Author 3. (2024).
Article title. Journal title, 18(3), 8516.
<https://doi.org/10.xxxx/XYZxxxxABCD>.

Style

Copyright (c) 2024 Authors

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Referencing

- 1. References.** A list of sources cited throughout the text that provide supporting information, prior research, or context for the study, acknowledging the work of other researchers and enabling readers to locate original sources for further study. Use standardised citation styles (e.g., APA, MLA, Chicago) to ensure consistency and facilitate accurate identification of sources. When deciding which citation style to use in your journal(s), you should give preference to those that include DOI or URL in reference list entries (e.g. APA, Chicago) and always display DOIs and URLs as links.
- 2. Supporting information:** Providing links to related research outputs (e.g. research data deposited in repositories, preprints, and registered studies, etc.) in the metadata of a journal article enhances the transparency, reproducibility, and discoverability of research. Use persistent identifiers to establish links with the related content.
- 3. How to cite.**